

Manufacture of the PLLA/BaTiO₃ fiber for fibrous piezoelectric sensor

H.J. Oh¹, D.K. Kim¹, and B.J. Yeang^{1*}

¹ Technical Textile R&D Group, Korea Institute of Industrial Technology, Ansan, Republic of Korea

* Byeong Jin Yeang (yeong777@kitech.re.kr)

Introduction

- To develop the green piezoelectric materials for replacing conventional ceramic and polymeric piezoelectric materials, Poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA)-based polymers was investigated. Poly (lactic acid) (PLLA) based piezoelectric materials are gradually becoming the substitute for the conventional piezoelectric materials due to their low cost and processability, biodegradable, non-toxic, piezoelectric and non-pyroelectric nature. However, it generally has lower piezo-responses than PVDF or conventional PZT based ceramic materials.
- The β -form structure in PLLA related to piezoelectric performance could be enhanced by controlling the post processing technique as well as adding ferroelectric particles such as lead zirconate-titanate (PZT), barium titanate (BTO), Iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) and zinc oxide (ZnO).

Research objective: To improve the piezoelectric properties of melt-spun poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA)/BaTiO₃ for wearable sensor applications, we optimized the post-processing conditions to increase the proportion of the β crystalline phase.

Experimental

1. Materials

PLLA (6201D, 99.9% L-type, Nature works, USA)
BaTiO₃ nanoparticle (300~ 500 nm, Lumi M Co.Ltd)

2. Melt-spinning conditions

Throughput rate: 0.46 g/min
Spinning temperature: 200°C
Spinneret: Φ 0.25
Take-up velocity of winder: 1 km/min

Table 1. Sample label with a various draw temperature and draw ratio.

	Sample name	BTO wt. %	Draw temperature	Draw ratio
	As-spun	3	0	1
Draw temp.	T90	3	90	3
	T100	3	100	3
	T110	3	110	3
	T120	3	120	3
	T130	3	130	3
Draw ratio	D2	3	120	2
	D3	3	120	3
	D3.5	3	120	3.5

Fabrication of the textile device

❖ Process

Results & Discussion

❖ DSC

❖ 2D-WAXD

❖ Piezoelectric test (Textile devices)

➤ Discussion

- The crystal transition α to β in PLLA fiber was increased by increasing the drawing temperature and draw ratio in the pilot scale melt-spinning.
- Textile device shows the maximum output current and voltage were 911 nA and 0.62mV.